

IGVF 2012
Rome June, 3-8

22nd International Conference on Virus and other Graft Transmissible Diseases of Fruit Crops

22nd International Conference
on
**Virus and Other
Graft Transmissible
Diseases of Fruit Crops**

Rome, June 3-8, 2012

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Conference Hall CRA-PAV
Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale
Via Carlo Giuseppe Bertero, 22
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INCIDENCE OF FIGLEAF MOTTLE ASSOCIATED VIRUS AND PROTEINAC
VIRUS IN EASTERN PROVINCE OF SAUDI ARABIA

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The fig tree (*Ficus religiosa* L.) is grown in Saudi Arabia and is being affected by the plant virus diseases
fig leaf mottle and proteinac virus. The main symptoms are chlorotic and necrotic blotching
and yellowing of leaf veins. Samples were collected with consideration of the geographical
distribution and abundance of the cultivars from different areas of Eastern Saudi Arabia. Each sample was
consisted of 10-20 leaves. Samples were placed in a plastic bag at 4°C then transported to the
laboratory. The leaf discoids (1.5 cm) were cut from the affected and healthy leaves and stored in a
refrigerator. Samples were extracted in 1 ml of grinding buffer. Crude was centrifuged with a
microcentrifuge and stored at -20°C. All steps of RNA extraction were done with 100 µl of product
NucleoSpin RNA extraction kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany). The RNA was quantified by 260/280 nm
absorbance ratio. The results were positive and negative controls. Mixed infections of fig leaf mottle
and proteinac virus. In our knowledge this is the first report on the incidence of these two RNA
viruses. Further studies are needed to investigate the prevalence of these viruses in the country.

POSTER SESSION I
FRUIT TREES:
VIRUSES, VIROIDS AND PHYTOPLASMAS

DETECTION AND MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF A NOVEL CRYPTOVIRUS FROM PERSIMMON (*DIOSPYROS KAKI*)

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Two dsRNA molecules with an estimated length of 1.5 Kbp were identified and characterized from leaves of a Japanese persimmon (*Diospyros kaki*) tree, showing veinlets necrosis on both sides of leaf blades. DOP-PCR recognized two genomic fragments of a bipartite cryptic virus, for which the name of Persimmon cryptic virus (PeCV) is proposed. RLM-RACE led to the sequencing of a 1,510 bp contig identified as dsRNA-1 and a 1,491 bp complete segment identified as dsRNA-2. The two genomic fragments resulted both monocistronic and harbored conserved domains related to RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRP) and capsid protein (CP) of species associated to *Alphacryptovirus* genus. Phylogenetic analysis of RdRP sequence showed highest amino acid identity with Black raspberry cryptic virus (BrCV, 63 %), Pepper cryptic virus 2 (PCV-2, 52 %) and -1 (PCV-1, 46 %). Whereas the CP putatively encoded by dsRNA-2 shared highest identity with Mulberry cryptic virus 1 (MCV-1, 49 %), PCV-2 (39 %) and PCV-1 (32 %). N-J phylogenetic analysis confirmed those relationships and delivered PeCV in a cluster with phyto-cryptoviruses belonging to genera *Alpha-* and *Betacryptovirus*, quite far distinguished from myco-cryptoviruses, gathered in genus *Partitivirus*. Virus-specific primers for RT-PCR were successfully designed inside the CP region to detect PeCV in several symptomless trees found in different orchards of Apulia (Southern Italy), thus proving that infection may be fairly common and presumably latent. An antiserum (kindly provided by Dr. M. Turina, CNR-IVV, Torino, Italy) specific to the CP of family-related *Beet cryptic virus 2* (BCV-2) was profitably used for western blot detection of a 45-50 KDa band, coherent with predicted size of dsRNA-2 product. Furthermore, antibodies were useful for ISEM observation and subsequent decoration of PeCV particles, proved to be isometric, around 30 nm in diameter, with rounded shape lacking in fine structural details, not easily permeable by negative stain.